

A Case on Faisal Hospital: Psychological and Administrative Issues During the Covid19 Pandemic

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Abstract:- Faisal hospital was among one the international hospitals dealing with different human medical conditions and gave prompt diagnosis and treatment. The hospital which is located on canal road Peoples colony Faisalabad performed well-appreciated duties during Covid19 pandemic. The case study's primary goal was to sort out some problems occur during the pandemic which was as follow: Due to overloaded cases in the Faisalabad region hospital suffered from some sorts of health issues such as psychological health issues raised among health workers, physically issues due to workload in hospital staff, the hospital also faced a shortage of Doctors and staff during the pandemic. Administrative issues such as mismanagement of doctor's schedule, roster duties, and staff shifts. The data examined in this case study provides information about administrative problems and psychological issues. Resulted in that they must have to concern with well-trained administrative officers to plan how to escape from such administrative crises raised during Covid19 pandemic.

I. INTRODUCTION

Dr. Muhammad Masood is among one of the best and well trained, talented doctors serving in Faisal hospital, Faisalabad. He joins the organization as one of the trustees of this hospital. He served his well-appreciated duties in the hospital in the concerned diagnostic laboratory, as well as also served as an educational institute head because of his vast experience in teaching and also due to his fabulous administrative record. One seminar highlights the issues raised during Covid 19 in the whole country. It became a concern talk which mentions some administrative and psychological issues raised in Faisal hospital due to the workload in covid 19 pandemic.

Faisal Hospital is an independent, not-for-profit acute care hospital Located at 673-A, Canal Bank Road, Peoples Colony, Faisalabad, Beginning in 2009, they provide outstanding in-patient and out-patient facilities with an emphasis on the safety and comfort of our patients and their loved ones .They are one of the greatest options in the nation because to their cutting-edge infrastructure and facilities that meet international standards. They strive to provide all local and foreign patients with high-quality healthcare services at reasonable pricing. The comprehensive array of medical, surgical, diagnostic, and wellness programs available at Faisal Hospital represent. The primary factor influencing patients' decisions to receive

care at Faisal Hospital is its convenient location. The hospital admits to caring for more than 23,000 patients each year. and it nearly 350,000 outpatient procedures. Patients from throughout the nation may rely on them to produce an excellent result thanks to their cutting-edge surgical technique, innovative research, and community involvement. The "patient service department" at Faisal Hospital is a distinct division that interacts with patient attendants and provides essential information at each stage in a way that is more appealing to people.

For analysis of psychological issues in covid patients and staff dealing with covid including doctors, nurses, and nonmedical staff meeting with well-trained and having excellent achievements in the field meeting with Hafiza Doctor Sadia Khan consultant psychologists serving in Faisal hospital. As a result of the meeting, the conclusion come to point that anxiety, personality disorder, phobia, economical issues, the schizophrenia will be generalized with hallucinations, and delusions which resulted in impairment in daily life functioning. Along with it phobia, there was some sort of psychological issues arise among couples due to sexual impairments which affect their personal life. That problem was highly seen among medical staff including doctors and nurses. In relevant to this one of the studies reported by Tengilimoglu et al. (2022) resulted that the worry of spreading the COVID-19 virus to their family is the main source of stress or anxiety among healthcare workers (86.9%). It has been found that female employees have higher levels of stress, anxiety, and depression than male employees. From the whole data analyzed that there was a huge list of psychological disorders which were seen during COVID 19 pandemic. The present study focused on some of these psychological issues and administrative issues.

II. ADMINISTRATION ISSUES DURING COVID-19

Dr. Muhammad Masood is among one of the best and well trained, talented doctors in Faisal hospital. During covid 19 pandemic situation became worst as Covid 19 effect all over the world frequently. Dr. Masood was also worried about the current situation, how to tackle such a situation, and how to run a hospital during the pandemic. To overcome this situation Dr. Masood recalls meeting with his staff to tackle and handle the worst condition. In this meeting, everyone was worried about the virus. Everyone brief their ideas which helped to handle that worst situation because there was no proper treatment at that time, also not

enough space to deal with patients.

Faisal hospital was among one the international hospital dealing with different human medical conditions and gave prompt diagnosis and treatment. Faisal hospital was located at a prime location in Faisalabad city. It performed well-appreciated duties during Covid19 pandemic. Due to overloaded cases in the Faisalabad region hospital suffer from some sorts of health issues such as psychological health issues raised among health workers, and physical issues due to the workload of hospital staff, the hospital also faced a shortage of Doctors and staff during a pandemic. Administrative issues such as mismanagement of doctors' schedules.

III. KEY ISSUES FACING

➤ Problems that Arise During Covid 19 Pandemic in A Hospital Setting

As covid pandemic was one of the worst conditions that spread worldwide and affect almost every aspect of life and every field. It affects the economic settings of every person, affects health both physically and mentally, and effective human resource power. Dr. Masood focuses on the problems in a hospital setting. According to relevant data as presented in figure 1 death rate in Pakistan was very high. So, a major problem in a hospital setting is the lack of medical facilities such as a lack of medicines because during the first layer no one was aware of proper treatment so no proper medication was available, and no vaccine was available. Due to this hospitals face problems like shortage of medicines, and shortage of proper diagnostic facilities. As well as during the first layer due to social media due to situation in other countries everyone suffers from a phobia, also staff suffered from Covid 19 which resulted in a shortage of doctors and health staff.

Fig 1 As of September 12, 2020, the Pakistani Covid 19 Active Cases, Recovery Vs. Fatality Rate

➤ Administrative Issues During And After Covid19 Pandemic

As covid 19 pandemic affect every organization at the start of the pandemic because no one was aware of the situation how to tackle it and how to handle patients infected with covid 19 virus. So major administrative problems that were seen in the hospital setting of Faisal hospital were the lack of quarantine rooms and centers. There were no sufficient gas cylinders. There was a shortage of medicines and an overall lack of all medical facilities. According to the complain officer Muhammad Tariq Mehmood major

complains received were problems seen not a well-planned schedule of doctors, their roster duties were unplanned, and the workload on staff was extremely high. Due to covid phobia healthcare staff also not performing their duties properly. Secondly, as all of us know that covid is high contagious disease spread from one person to another there was an additional problem for hospital administration on how to manage waste produced from hospital wards of affected patients. How to maintain environment clean. How to protect others as it was one of the foremost important responsibilities of the medical field.

- Table 1 Provides an overview of some of the interview questions the interviewer asked hospital staff.

Table 1 The COVID 19-Related Evaluations of the Involved Healthcare Professionals

	n	%
Does your hospital have any patients with COVID-19 diagnoses?	Yes 1651	79.5
	No 425	20.5
Have you acquired a COVID-19 diagnosis?	Yes 64	3.1
	No 2012	96.6
	Never 740	35.6
How frequently do you contact with COVID-19 patients?	Sometimes 852	41.0
	Often 484	23.4
	Yes 517	24.9
Do you believe that your institution's anti-Covid-19 policies and procedures are adequate?	Partially 1174	56.6
	No 385	18.5
	Yes 15	0.7
Do you believe the populace will adhere to the rules?	Partially 577	27.8
	No 1484	71.5
	Yes 1012	48.7
Do you think that the Ministry of Health paying health professionals the highest performance is a good thing?	Partially 691	33.3
	No 373	18.0
	Positive 1483	71.4
How do you perceive the significant shift in societal perceptions of healthcare professionals?	Negative 593	28.6

➤ *Quantity of Workload on Staff During Covid19 Pandemic:*

Faisal international hospital had a lot of employees which consist of 60% health workers and 40% physicians. All of them perform their duties accordingly to their assigned schedule in the morning and night shifts. According to nursing superintendent Shaheena Parveen increased ratio of Covid cases in the Faisalabad region hospital also suffered from a high workload which result in the mismanagement of staff duties in both shifts. This issue was raised due to mismanagement of the HRM department. Which not performed their duties in a timely and did not make a proper schedule as well as did not inform the timing of duties to staff including clinical and non-clinical staff and also to OPD patients. The estimated affected countries and workload according to the rate of the affected population are shown in figure 2

The Most affected countries from COVID-19

Fig 2 The Most Affected Countries from COVID-19

➤ *Protection and Safety of Health Workers:*

Faisal hospital was among one of the best private hospitals which care for a lot of their employees both clinical including doctors, physicians, and health workers as well as non-clinical staff including ward staff cleaning staff, and administrative staff. Among the board of trustees Dr Tauqeer Cheema assigned separate funds for the safety and protection of staff.

All funds contributed to purchase of safety and personal protective equipment such as sanitizer, face masks, gloves, and foot wears. As the covid19 pandemic goes to its worst it affects all sides Prices of all personal protective equipment's raised to the sky because everyone was unemployed so it was a chance for pharmacies and factories to earn their profit at peak and old all required things at a high rate. This disturbed the hospital-assigned funds for the safety of health workers. Due to this, there was a lack of health facilities for health workers. Health workers had to deal with all such health issues due to a lack of funds for health.

IV. RELEVANT READING AND REFERENCE

➤ *Prior to examining this case, Students ought to be informed of the concept of covid19 pandemic and it related financial crisis in developing countries they will better comprehend the theory after reading the passages that follow.*

- Ahmad, M., Beg, B. M., s, H. S. M., & Ullah, A. (2021). COVID-19 pandemic control and administrative issues in Pakistan: How Pakistan mitigated both pandemic and administration issues?. *Journal of Public Affairs*, e2760.
- <http://www.faisalhospital.com/AboutUs.html>
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- Wang C, Wang D, Abbas J, Duan K, Mubeen R. Global Financial Crisis, Smart Lockdown Strategies, and the COVID-19 Spillover Impacts: A Global Perspective Implications From Southeast Asia. *Front Psychiatry*. 2021 Sep 3;12:643783. doi: 10.3389/fpsy.2021.643783. PMID: 34539457; PMCID: PMC844639.

V. A CASE ON FAISAL HOSPITAL: PSYCHOLOGICAL AND ADMINISTRATIVE ISSUES DURING THE COVID19 PANDEMIC

❖ *Teaching Notes*

➤ *Case Synopsis*

Faisal hospital was among one the international hospitals dealing with different human medical conditions and gave prompt diagnosis and treatment. The hospital which is located on canal road Peoples colony Faisalabad performed well-appreciated duties during Covid19 pandemic. The case study's primary goal was to sort out some problems occur during the pandemic which was as follow: Due to overloaded cases in the Faisalabad region hospital suffered from some sorts of health issues such as psychological health issues raised among health workers, physically issues due to workload in hospital staff, the hospital also faced a shortage of Doctors and staff during the pandemic. Administrative issues such as mismanagement of doctor's schedule, roster duties, and staff shifts.

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From the whole data analyzed that there was a huge list of psychological disorders which were seen during Covid 19 pandemic. The present case study focused on some of these psychological issues and some administrative issues.

➤ *Case Objective*

The main objectives of the concern case study were as follows:

- This case study can be used to teach human resource development courses at the under-graduate level. It was written for business and public administration programs.
- The purpose of the case study is to familiarize students with real-life administrative issues that prevail in the hospital.
- The case study encourages the students to research such topics.

- To enlighten the psychological issues that arise in Pakistan among Health workers

➤ *Case Study Questions*

- What are the main problems arising during the covid 19 pandemic in a hospital setting?
- What were the administrative issues during and after covid19 pandemic?
- What was the quantity of workload on stuff during covid19 pandemic?
- What were the health issues raised in health workers during covid19 pandemic?
- How much funds were assigned for the protection and safety of health workers?
- Is hospital rooms and beds enough for admitted patients in the Covid19 Pandemic?

VI. ANALYSIS OF DATA

➤ *What are the Main Problems that Arise During Covid 19 Pandemic in A Hospital Setting?*

As one of the worst diseases to ever strike the world, the covid epidemic affected practically every sphere of human endeavor. It has an impact on everyone's economic circumstances, physical and mental health, and the availability of human resources. The issues in the hospital context are the main focus of the current case study investigation.

According to the pertinent data shown in figure 1 Pakistan's death rate was extremely high. Therefore, a key issue in a hospital setting is a shortage of medical resources, such as medicines. In the beginning, no one was aware of the correct therapy, so neither proper medications nor vaccines were available. As a result, hospitals encounter issues like a lack of adequate diagnostic tools and medications. Everyone experienced phobias during the First Layer owing to social media and the circumstances in other nations, and staff members also experienced COVID-19, which led to a scarcity of medical professionals.

Fig 3 COVID-19 by Region, as of September

➤ *What were the Administrative Issues During and After Covid19 Pandemic?*

Because no one knew how to handle the issue and patients who were infected with the covid 19 virus at the beginning of the pandemic, the covid 19 pandemic affected every organization. Therefore, a significant administrative issue that was seen in the Faisal Hospital's hospital environment was the lack of quarantine centers and rooms. There weren't enough gas cylinders available. There were not enough medical facilities overall, nor were there enough medications.

There were issues with poorly planned doctor schedules, unforeseen roster tasks, and a colossal workload for the staff, according to administrative responsibilities. Healthcare workers are not completing their responsibilities as they should because of covid fear. Second, since it is common knowledge that COVID is a highly contagious illness that spreads from person to person, hospital management faced a new challenge in managing the waste products from affected patients' hospital wards. How to keep the environment tidy. How to protect others, as that was one of the medical profession's top priorities. Table 2 provides a summary of some of the questions the interviewer asked hospital workers.

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➤ *What was the Quantity of Workload on Staff During Covid19 Pandemic?*

Faisal international hospital had a lot of employees which consist of 60% health workers and 40% physicians. All of them perform their duties accordingly to their assigned schedule the in morning and night shifts. Due to the increased ratio of Covid cases in the Faisalabad region hospital also suffered from a high workload which result in the mismanagement of staff duties in both shifts. This issue was raised due to mismanagement of the HRM department. They failed to complete their tasks on time, failed to create an appropriate schedule, and failed to advise other staff members—both clinical and non-clinical—as well as OPD patients—of the timing of their tasks. As indicated in figure 1.2 with the predicted affected countries and workload based on the rate of the affected population.

The Most affected countries from COVID-19

Fig 4 COVID-19 affected countries worldwide - February 15, 2021.

➤ *What were the Health Issues Raised in Health Workers During Covid19 Pandemic?*

As Faisal hospital was consist of 60% health workers. The main concern of the case study is to asses any health or psychological issue raised by health workers of Faisal hospital during covid19 pandemic. Covid19 pandemic affects the lives of normal as well as all the employed population. In this time period every one suffers from lockdown their lives become miserable. All the health workers got trapped between their domestic issues and employment issues. There was the huge sort of workload on them with danger to their own lives as they had to deal day and night with the covid patient in rooms ICU on ventilators. This causes some psychiatric issues among health workers, Such as anxiety, depression, Schizophrenia, hallucination, delusion, fatigue, and acute stress syndrome. Due to the shortage of staff health workers have to deal with patients in ICU continuously wearing PPE which also cause skin issue among doctors and health workers staff. Some of the relevant questions from hospital staff were summarized in table 3

Table 3 Healthcare Professionals' Perspectives on the Conditions Generating Stress or Worry

What do you think about the scenario you're in or the things that worry you?	n	%
Worry that my relatives or parents will spread the COVID-19 virus	1808	87.0
Phobia of getting the virus	1145	55.1
Experiencing a family member's death	1113	52.6
Missing family members whilst being away from them	983	47.5
Infecting my patients with the virus	689	33.1
Failing to fulfill my family's social needs	684	33.4
Afraid of dying	595	28.7
Not fulfill my family's necessities, such as providing food	435	21.0

➤ *How Much Fund was Assigned for Protection and Safety of Health Workers?*

One of the top private hospitals, Faisal Hospital showed great concern for all of its employees, including both clinical personnel such as physicians, nurses, and other medical specialists, as well as non-clinical like ward staff, cleaning staff, and administrative staff. The staff's security and protection were given separate budgets by the board of trustees. Each and every dollar donated will be used to purchase safety and personal protection equipment, including hand sanitizer, face masks, gloves, and shoes. The COVID-19 pandemic is affecting everyone as it reaches its peak. The fact that everyone was unemployed during this time caused the prices of all personal protective equipment to soar, giving pharmacists and factories the opportunity to make a hefty profit while also selling the obsolete stock at a premium. This upset the hospital, which had allocated money for the security of medical personnel. As a result, there were not enough medical facilities for the medical personnel. Due to the shortage of funding for health as shown in table 4, health personnel had to cope with all of these health conditions.

Table 4 The Perspectives of Healthcare Workers Regarding Issues Relating to the Working Environment.

Issues	N	%
Personal protective equipment deficiency	1017	48.5
Administrative issues	722	35.3
Workplace ventilation is insufficient	538	27.0
Absence of specific diagnoses, procedures, and information	480	23.1
Difficulty in reporting equipment shortages, etc., to Managers.	432	20.8
No defined COVID-19 triage	427	21.1
Owing to the COVID-19 outbreak, working while ill	365	15.1
Engaging in work unrelated to one's field of expertise	355	15.3
Not hiring more personnel for the department after the COVID-19 outbreak	339	16.2
Not having the option to refrain from working under hazardous conditions, such as when pregnant or older than 65.	114	5.0

➤ *Is Hospital Rooms and Beds Enough for Admitted Patients in the Covid19 Pandemic?*

All the private sector hospital was fully furnished and provides almost all the faculties for the comfort of their patients. One of the best private hospitals in Faisal international hospital. As it treated up to 25000 admitted patients and gave treatment to 350000 patients annually. Most of the private hospitals are approximately 120 bedded hospitals with full facilities which were enough for normal routine. This case study was about covid19 pandemic. Some of the relevant studies it proved data about the ratio of admitted patients in government sectors in table 5.

Table 5 Government of Pakistan Emergency Health Plans by Province

	Designated hospitals	Isolation center	Beds	Quarantine center	Testing labs	Ventilators
Punjab	5	50	955	10948	35	324
Sindh	7	4	151	2100	21	200
AJK	4	110	857	2761	23	171
Baluchistan	11	15	535	5898	7	N/A
KPK	4	14	32	532	5	12
GB	3	20	127	973	5	6
ICT	2	3	11	350	16	N/A
Total	36	216	2947	23562	112	713

Faisal hospital was 120 bedded hospital during the pandemic covid there was a huge burden of patients who tested strongly positive for covid. Their health conditions were not enough good to discharge them. For the betterment of humanity and ethics, all should have to remain on ventilators to protect their lives. Quarantine them and provide all the basic facilities hospital had to admit them. The hospital suffered from a shortage of beds and rooms for covid patients during Covid pandemic.

VII. CONCLUSION

The data examined in this case study provides information that how private sector as well as government sector hospitals in developing countries suffered from administrative problems and psychological issues. They must have to concern with well-trained administrative officers to plan how to escape from such administrative crises raised during Covid19 pandemic. This study help business study how to tackle such administrative problems during their practical lives. To assess the administrative problems in any organization. As well as how to do interdepartmental research such as in concern to medical field like how to analyze data about psychological findings and interpret it. And answer their solution as all of them arise due to a lack in administrative and human resource management responsibilities which is relevant to business studies.

➤ *Teaching Plan*

Table 6 Teaching Plan

Sr Num:	Activity	Time
01	every student read it carefully	20 minutes
02	Brain storming/Discussion	25 minutes
03	Answer of each question	51 minutes(9mins*6 questions)

REFERENCES

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